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Show us what you got!

A cross-cultural comparison of mindset presentation in “...Got Talent!” TV shows

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Abstract

Media impact people's beliefs and reflect shared cultural values. One of the most popular TV and online program formats are *talent shows*, where people present skills from different domains and are assessed by a panel of celebrity judges. This kind of media content is rich in information about the presumed nature of abilities. In the paper, we examine how mindsets—the implicit theories regarding the innate or malleable nature of abilities—are expressed in talent shows in three countries differing in individualism and collectivism: China, Poland, and USA. Through quantitative thematic analysis, we found significant differences across cultures in how often each mindset (fixed, growth, and mixed) was shared by participants, judges, and other people who appeared in the shows. While the growth mindset was most strongly underlined by participants from China and least strongly by those from the USA, the fixed mindset was mainly articulated by judges in the Polish version of the show. We discuss results in the light of collectivism/individualism and modernization theory.

Keywords: fixed and growth mindset; individualism, collectivism, talent show, media

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Sometimes, TV show formats can take a nation’s breath away, gluing families to the screen on a weekly basis. Although we often fall prey to the popular misconception that the media impact others more strongly than ourselves (Sun et al., 2008), we can hardly evade the impact of shows that conquer the globe and are broadcasted in various nations (e.g., Bandura, 2001; Pajares et al., 2009). One such case is apparent for the “...Got Talent!” format, a talent show, where people present their skills to an audience and celebrity judges. For example, the first run of Britain’s Got Talent (2007) told the story of a “lump of coal turning into a diamond” (an initial reaction voiced by one of the judges after the first performance), most of us are probably familiar with: the one of Paul Potts (Locke, 2009). Indeed, the medial portrayal of highly skilled people often romanticizes the “rocky road” the candidates had to endure until this point, or reinforces some stereotypes, for example, intellectual brilliance accompanied by negative socio-emotional skills like in the case of Sherlock Holmes or Dr. Sheldon Cooper from the *Big Bang Theory* show (Baudson, 2016; Winston, 2016). Yet, little is known about how media presents the nature of (creative) skills, a vital aspect in the case of talent shows: Are these skills viewed as inborn, unchangeable traits, or rather as the result of effort and learning?

In this paper, we aim to answer this question based on a quantitative thematic content analysis of the globally broadcasted TV program “...Got Talent!”. We start by describing implicit theories regarding the malleable or fixed nature of abilities, with a focus on creativity. We then highlight the cultural differences in the expression of mindsets. Finally, we present the results of a cross-cultural study, which compared the nature of abilities presented in the show among three countries that differ in their levels of individualism and collectivism—China, Poland, and the USA.

Implicit Theories of Abilities: Growth, Fixed, or Mixed Mindsets

Lay conceptions of psychological phenomena reflect “common-cultural views” and are called *implicit theories* (Sternberg, 1985). They rarely converge to professional knowledge, and people are not always fully aware of them. Still, they guide many everyday decisions (e.g., Karwowski et al., 2019; Wickes & Ward, 2006). In recent years, attention was drawn to implicit theories of the nature of abilities: growth and fixed mindsets. Fixed mindsets reflect the inborn nature of skills (e.g., intelligence, creativity), whereas growth mindsets (also called malleable, or incremental mindsets) underline the role of effort and work in cultivating skills (Dweck, 2000).

These beliefs play an essential regulatory function impacting motivation, attribution, and behavior when facing challenges (Burnette et al., 2013; Dweck & Moden, 2005). People who hold malleable mindsets endorse *mastering goals*, more strongly focusing on development and improvement. People with a fixed mindset more typically pick *performance-approach goals*, wanting to show off and outperform others, or *performance-avoidance goals*, avoiding the risk of being seen as incompetent (Blackwell et al., 2007). In case someone perceives abilities as permanent, one is reluctant to test new skills and invest energy in demanding activities (Miele & Molden, 2010). Difficulties are treated as proof of insufficient skill and threaten self-esteem, leading to risk avoidance (Dweck, 2000). In contrast, believing in malleable characteristics of abilities helps to persevere when facing difficulties, motivates to take a risk or to set ambitious goals (Mrazek et al., 2018; Mueller & Dweck, 1998; Sarrasin et al., 2018). In consequence, holding a growth mindset was associated with greater achievements (e.g., Blackwell et al., 2007; Sisk et al., 2018; Yeager & Dweck, 2012). So far, one could view these two mindsets as opposing ends of a continuum—if people are convinced that some abilities are stable, they should be confident that they are unchangeable. Yet, it was suggested that “[i]t is perfectly possible for an individual to hold both theories” (Dweck et al., 1995b, p. 323). Indeed, explorations specifically focusing on creative mindsets

found that they are separate constructs, not opposite ends; therefore, people can endorse both simultaneously (Hass et al., 2016; Puente-Diaz & Cavazos-Arroyo, 2017; but see also O'Connor et al., 2013; for a comprehensive discussion of this issue, see Karwowski & Brzeski, 2017; Karwowski et al., 2019a), implicating a *mixed* mindset representation.

The interest in mindsets research started with investigations of beliefs regarding intelligence and academic performance (Dweck, 2000), but as of today, various other domains (cf. Rahnama & Popkowski Leszczyc, 2022), such as creativity (Karwowski, 2014), have been looked at. Entity theorists (i.e., people with fixed mindsets regarding creativity) show low interest in creativity (O'Connor et al., 2013) and are less engaged in creative thinking (Pretz & Nelson, 2017). Consequently, they distrust their creative ability (Hass et al., 2016), perform worse in creativity tasks (Karwowski, 2014; O'Connor et al., 2013), and report fewer creative achievements (O'Connor et al., 2013; Puente-Diaz & Cavazos-Arroyo, 2017). Incremental theorists (i.e., people with growth mindsets) are the opposite: They are more creative (Karwowski, 2014; Karwowski et al., 2019a; O'Connor et al., 2013) and believe more strongly in their creativity (Hass et al., 2016). The characteristics of people who share a high level of both mindsets are more complicated—they present above-average levels of creative skills, moderate levels of creative activities and achievements, but a high level of creative self-beliefs (Karwowski et al., 2019a).

One of the remaining questions regarding mindsets, including creative ones, involves the factors that influence these beliefs. There is evidence that mindsets are shaped by social relations rooted in cultural values, for example, through parenting and teaching beliefs and behaviors (e.g., Jose & Bellamy, 2012; Mesler et al., 2021; Karwowski et al., 2020). In the subsequent section of the article, we will delve into the connection between growth and fixed mindsets and cultural experiences.

Cultural Differences in Mindsets

Mindsets, as implicit theories, are bound to social values and culture (Glăveanu, 2011; Runco & Johnson, 2002), and thus can be expected to differ across culture. For example, it was assumed that more individualistic cultures, where people focus on personal goals, will perceive abilities as fixed, inborn, and non-malleable (Dweck et al., 1995a, 1995b; Heine et al., 2001; Lillard 1998). Conversely, in more collectivist countries, where effort and common goals are valued more strongly, growth mindsets are assumed to be more prevalent (Dweck et al., 1995a, 1995b; Heine et al., 2001; Lillard, 1998). Indeed, people from Asia perceived abilities as more malleable than people from Western countries (Stevenson & Lee, 1990; Stevenson & Stigler, 1992; but for opposite results, see Dong & Kang, 2022; Sun et al., 2021).

A more detailed picture was presented in research regarding cross-cultural differences in creative mindsets (Tang et al., 2016). The syndromes of culture—collectivism and individualism—were intersected by vertical and horizontal social orientations (Singelis et al., 1995; Triandis & Gelfand, 1998). The vertical dimension reflects a focus on differences and hierarchies among people, while the horizontal dimension emphasizes similarities between people. The cross-section of cultural syndromes and social dimensions results in four different categories of cultural expression: (1) *Horizontal Individualism*: when individuals are distinct but not distinguished from each other; (2) *Vertical Individualism*: a tendency to focus on people's acquired status and uniqueness; (3) *Horizontal Collectivism*: a focus on common goals and values; (4) *Vertical Collectivism*: emphasis on in-group integrity (see Table 1; Singelis et al., 1995; Triandis & Gelfand, 1998).

Table 1.

Characteristics of Horizontal and Vertical Individualism and Collectivism (Adapted from Singelis et al., 1995; Tang et al., 2016; Triandis & Gelfand, 1998).

Individualism	Collectivism
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Horizontal social orientation	People are distinct but not distinguished from each other	Common goals and values
	Focus on self-reliance	Focus on interdependence, sociability, and hedonism
	High freedom	Low freedom
	High equality	High equality
Vertical social orientation	Status and uniqueness	In-group integrity
	Focus on competition and hedonism	Focus on tradition, authoritarianism, and sociability
	High freedom	Low freedom
	Low equality	Low equality

Each cultural orientation relates differently to creative mindsets: A study by Tang and colleagues (2016) found that entity theorists were more closely linked to vertical individualism, and holders of incremental beliefs were more strongly associated with the horizontal dimension (both individually and collectively). The study recruited samples from Poland and Germany, the former being more individualistic (i.e., both vertically and horizontally), perceiving creativity as more fixed and less malleable than people from Germany. As Germans were generally more collectivistic, they presented a higher incremental and lower fixed view of creativity. In addition, individualism and collectivism fully mediated the countries' differences in mindset preference (Tang et al., 2016). The even stronger focus on fixed mindsets in Poland as compared to the already individualistic Germany (Hofstede, 1980) could be explained through modernization theory: Cultures with constant economic growth—as is the case for post-communist Poland—focus on social and economic progress and develop an individualistic orientation (Inglehart, 1997; Kashima et al., 2004).

Based on theoretical foundations and research findings, we anticipate substantial differences in the way beliefs about the variable or innate nature of abilities are held. In cultures that value individualism and the distinctiveness of individuals, one can expect beliefs about the unchanging character of abilities to prevail. Conversely, in more collectivistic cultures, it seems reasonable to expect that beliefs emphasizing the central role of effort will be more common. Nevertheless, the question remains as to whether these tendencies will be apparent in popular media contents.

Mindsets, Media, and Culture: Present Study

Mindsets are malleable: Even short and simple interventions can change what people think regarding the roots of abilities (Karwowski et al., 2020b). Consuming media is not an exception, impacting the audience's implicit beliefs (Ceh & Lebuda, 2022; Happer & Philo, 2013). Yet, people who rely more strongly on popular media sources of information are more prone to believe in myths about creativity, intelligence, and learning (Benedek et al., 2021), suggesting that the media might be an omnipresent, yet not always valid source of information.

Beliefs about the nature of abilities may well be derived from talent shows, where people showcase their skills in different domains and are assessed by a panel of celebrities. The socially laden feedback the performers receive fulfills a central precondition for observational learning (e.g., Bandura, 2001, 2002; Pajares et al., 2009; Potter & Riddle, 2007). Arguably, the most popular program within this category is “... Got Talent!” – a TV and social media phenomenon that has aired in 194 countries, the most social-media broadcasted series in 2019 (reaching 3.2 billion views; <https://www.nbc.com/americas-got-talent/about>, accessed March 26, 2022). A qualitative content analysis of semi-finals from three countries with different levels of individualism and collectivism—China, Poland, and the U.S—indicated cultural differences in mindset representation (Lebuda & Karwowski, 2023). Across all countries, growth mindsets were expressed through appreciation of effort and work. In China, the necessity of social support and the

presence of a mentor were emphasized for the development of abilities. On the other hand, the Polish version underlined the individualistic character of achievements: Participants highlighted the role of their dedication and solitude in their development. Even though there was evidence for the presence of fixed mindsets in each country, it was especially salient in the Polish version by labelling performers as being geniuses, gifted, or artists. While the qualitative analysis revealed different forms of how fixed and growth mindset were evident in these countries, a quantitative analysis is missing to examine how strongly these mindsets were expressed by performers and judges, and whether these mindset levels differ across countries. Therefore, the aim of this study is to investigate differences in the extent of mindset expression in a multinational dataset of “...Got Talent!” semi-final performances, focusing on the extent of growth, fixed, and mixed mindset expression in three countries that vary along the collectiveness-individualism dimension: China, Poland, and the USA.

Methods

This study was pre-registered (<https://aspredicted.org/gp89c.pdf>).

Participants

We analyzed performances by all 82 semi-finalist performers from the 2020 season of “... Got Talent!” in China ($n = 20$), Poland ($n = 40$), and the USA ($n = 22$). No data were excluded. These countries were chosen for the analysis because significant differences in terms of collectivism and individualism have been noted among them. China is a country which ranks high in terms of collectivism ($d = 0.66$ higher compared to the US). The US ranks higher in individualism than China ($d = 0.46$) and Poland ($d = 0.16$; Oyserman, Coon, & Kemmelmeier, 2002).

Procedure

For each performance, the videographic material, available on the national webpage of the talent show, was supplemented by a transcript. Three judges watched each performance at least twice, and then proceeded to read the transcript to score the intensity of fixed, growth, and mixed mindset (additional variables are reported in the supplement). The Chinese version was transcribed by a sinologist and extended by comments on cultural references that occurred during the show. Each judge was trained in the psychology of self-beliefs, especially mindsets. The first author of the manuscript trained the judges: The training for the assessment was conducted based on the Polish version of the program from the 2019 edition. The assessment was done independently. The qualitative data from this research will be published separately (Lebuda & Karwowski, 2023).

Measures

Mindsets

Three independent raters evaluated the extent of mindset expression by the participants, judges (i.e., all judges for a given participant were evaluated together), and others (i.e., people other than participants and judges appearing on the show) on a scale from 1 (very little) to 7 (very strongly). This was done separately for each mindset type (growth, fixed, and mixed). An example of a strong expression of growth mindset was for instance:

“I usually practice 6 days a week. Probably the best for me is to practice alone, especially if I learn some new things, I prefer to focus on it and do my own thing, learning from some mistakes. I’m very critical of myself here. Well, every shortcoming bothers me. I think it helps that I have the special drive to become better and better. I was surprised myself that the progress was so fast.” (participant, Poland)

An example of a strong expression of fixed mindset is: *“A young singer with an angelic voice. Such a voice is extremely rare, we should cultivate such a talent.”* (host, China), and an example of a mixed mindset is:

“Well, I think I loved the themes that you pick and like you said, your words are definitely the window to your soul, because we sit here and we definitely get you, we feel what you're feeling. It's unbelievable. It's such a special talent that you have, and I hope that America loves what you're doing as much as we all love it.” (judge, the USA)

In total, there were nine rating dimensions per performance. Inter-rater-reliability was high for each dimension (see Table 2); thus, ratings were averaged across the three raters. Mean ratings for each combination of mindset type and perspective are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Descriptive statistics and intraclass-correlation coefficients (ICC) with their 95% confidence interval (CI), and inter-correlations for the mindset types (fixed, growth, and mixed) as expressed by the different perspectives of performers, judges, and others.

	Perspective	Mindset	M (SD)	ICC	95% CI	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1		fixed	2.01 (1.01)	.89	[.84; .92]								
2	Performers	growth	2.84 (1.29)	.89	[.84; .93]	-.03							
3		mixed	1.38 (0.49)	.69	[.55; .79]	.07	.13						
4		fixed	3.14 (1.36)	.88	[.82; .92]	.14	.09	-.13					
5	Judges	growth	2.39 (1.21)	.83	[.75; .88]	-.06	.25	.09	-.23				
6		mixed	1.67 (0.62)	.72	[.60; .81]	-.10	-.07	.06	-.01	.29			
7		fixed	1.61 (0.97)	.89	[.85; .93]	.25	.21	.08	.26	.14	.05		
8	Others	growth	1.52 (0.79)	.88	[.82; .92]	-.03	.15	.22	.13	.05	-.05	.09	
9		mixed	1.10 (0.30)	.80	[.72; .87]	-.05	.14	.11	-.13	.22	-.02	.19	.18

Notes. $N = 82$; $|r| > .345$: $p < .001$; $|r| > .277$: $p < .01$, $|r| > .214$: $p < .05$.

Data analyses

The main analyses focused on comparison of mindsets across countries. An additional, preregistered line of analysis aiming to predict success in the talent show is reported in the supplement. The data for this study was processed and analyzed using *R* (v. 4.0.2., R Core Team, 2022). We used *apaTables* (Stanley, 2021), *car* (Fox & Weisberg, 2019), *emmeans* (Lenth, 2021), *Hmisc* (Harrell, 2021), *psych* (Revelle, 2021), and *tidyverse* (Wickham et al., 2019). Data, analysis scripts, and supplementary

materials are available on the Open Science Framework (https://osf.io/zd6bj/?view_only=3178c7a99bde46e8b4e7b44cbf33e2b0).

Results

Cross-cultural comparison

We ran a 3 x 3 x 3 ANOVA with the extent of mindset expression as dependent variable and country (China, Poland, USA), mindset type (fixed, growth, mixed), and perspective (performers, judges, others) as independent variables. The analysis revealed a significant main effect regarding country ($F_{2, 711} = 8.23, p < .001, \omega_p^2 = .02$), person ($F_{2, 711} = 74.44, p < .001, \omega_p^2 = .13$), and mindset ($F_{2, 711} = 73.03, p < .001, \omega_p^2 = .12$), as well as significant interactions between country and person ($F_{4, 711} = 4.19, p = .002, \omega_p^2 = .02$), country and mindset ($F_{4, 711} = 6.72, p < .001, \omega_p^2 = .03$), and person and mindset ($F_{4, 711} = 19.44, p < .001, \omega_p^2 = .09$). Finally, the three-way interaction country x person x mindset was significant ($F_{8, 711} = 2.89, p = .004, \omega_p^2 = .02$). Figure 1 shows the estimated marginal means for the three-way-interaction.

Figure 1. Estimated marginal means showing the extent of mindset expression for each combination of country, perspective, and mindset type.

A: Performers

As expected, growth mindsets were more strongly articulated by performers in China ($M = 3.42$), as compared to the USA ($M = 2.09$; $p < .001$), but not as compared to Poland ($M = 2.97$; $p = .174$). In addition, performers in Poland put greater emphasis on growth mindsets as compared to the USA ($p = .001$). There were no differences in the performer's expression of fixed and mixed mindsets between the three investigated countries (all p 's $> .148$ and $> .087$, respectively).

B: Judges

Judges in Poland more strongly displayed fixed mindsets ($M = 3.63$), as compared to both USA ($M = 2.56$; $p < .001$) and China ($M = 2.82$; $p = .004$). USA and China did not differ from each other regarding the expression of fixed mindsets for judges ($p = .639$). There were no differences in the judge's expression of growth and mixed mindsets between the three countries (all p 's $> .072$ and $> .311$, respectively).

C: Others

Looking at mindset expression by other interviewees, higher fixed mindset was reported in China ($M = 2.03$) compared to the USA ($M = 1.15$; $p = .006$), but neither China and Poland ($M = 1.64$; $p = .265$), nor USA and Poland ($p = .111$) differed from each other in this comparison. Interviewees in China ($M = 2.10$) more strongly emphasized growth mindsets as compared to both interviewees in the USA ($M = 1.17$; $p = .003$) and Poland ($M = 1.42$, $p = .019$). Interviewees in the USA did not differ from their Polish counterparts when it came to emphasizing growth mindsets ($p = .561$). Finally, there were no differences regarding the expression of mixed mindsets between the interviewees across the three countries (all p 's $> .822$).

Discussion

People's beliefs regarding abilities are not always conscious, nor in line with current scientific knowledge (Sternberg, 1985). Nevertheless, they play a vital role: They impact everyday decisions and behaviors (e.g., Karwowski et al., 2019). Beliefs regarding the innate or malleable nature of abilities have a crucial regulatory function for behavior (Dweck, 2000). It was presented in cross-cultural psychometric studies that cultural syndromes—individualism and collectivism—differentiate the perception of abilities in many domains (Dong & Kang, 2022; Sun et al., 2021; Stevenson & Lee, 1990; Stevenson & Stigler, 1992). For example, when it comes to creative mindsets, it has been found that people from more individualistic countries tend to believe that creativity is less malleable. Conversely, people from more collectivistic countries tend to exhibit less fixed and more incremental convictions regarding creativity (Tang et al., 2016). One critical source of knowledge and information transfer is through the media, but those who base their knowledge on media reports are especially prone to spreading myths about intelligence, learning and creativity (cf., Benedek et al., 2021). Therefore, how the media portray skills, especially the possibility to cultivating and developing them might be impacting the behaviors of the viewership. Our

main interest was to see whether these representations are different between countries with varying levels of individualism and collectivism.

Previous work conducted a qualitative analysis showing that mindsets were expressed in different forms between Chinese, Polish, and American editions of the show (Lebuda & Karwowski, 2023). This paper presents a quantitative analysis of the data to unveil potential differences in mindsets across countries as expressed by different perspectives of performers, judges and others. The expressions of mindsets were different between countries. Like in previous psychometric (Tang et al., 2016) and qualitative analyses (Lebuda & Karwowski, 2023), the growth mindset was most prevalent in the Chinese version of the program, and particularly strong for performers. In addition, Polish performers expressed incremental beliefs regarding the nature of abilities more intensely than their counterparts from the USA, but the Polish jury expressed significantly stronger fixed mindsets than those from both other countries. A more pronounced presentation of growth beliefs in collectivist countries was indicated theoretically (Dweck et al., 1995a, 1995b; Heine et al., 2001; Lillard, 1998) and displayed in empirical studies (Stevenson & Lee, 1990; Stevenson & Stigler, 1992), although the results were not always consistent (Dong & Kang, 2022; Sun et al., 2021). In that sense, the results in Poland and China seem particularly interesting, pointing to contradictory beliefs about the nature of abilities between performers and judges: While performers attributed their performance more in terms of training and development, judges attributed performances rather to innate talent. These findings could be interpreted in light of Poland's cultural context and the theory of modernization (Inglehart, 1997; Kashima et al., 2004). Poland, a former communist country, still has clear manifestations of a collectivist culture. Still, as a country that is dynamically developing and both socially and financially aspiring, it expresses individualistic attitudes more and more clearly (cf., Tang et al., 2016).

Implicit theories pertaining to the nature of abilities are readily identifiable in media content. This information could both present and reinforce commonly shared opinions. Further exploration of cultural

differences in mindsets expression can help to better understand cross-cultural diversity, e.g., in resilience (Skevington & WHOQOL SRPB Group, 2020; Ungar et al., 2005), feedback-related behavior (Ahn et al., 2016; Sully De Luque & Sommer, 2000), or even creativity (Guo et al., 2023) and countries' innovation (Rinne et al., 2012; Shane, 1992, 1993; Tian et al., 2018). Moreover, given that the media serve as a valuable avenue for vicarious learning, it is crucial to be mindful of the beliefs that are being portrayed and praised (Bandura 2002, 2004; Pajares et al. 2009). It is worth dedicating attention to selecting media content that facilitates the development of an agency towards challenges but also contributes to the cultivation of own skills, such as creativity (Ceh & Lebuda, 2022).

Limitations and Future Directions

The presented study went beyond acquiring a typically WEIRD representation of the world (Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic societies; Henrich, Heine, & Norenzayan, 2010) and performed a more emic analysis based on secondary data (Karwowski, 2016). Still, there are limitations to this study. First, the small number of participants doesn't allow for conducting all planned analyses, for example examining how performer and performance characteristics predict the mindset expressions in each country (see <https://aspredicted.org/gp89c.pdf>), and additional results in the supplement). Given that mindsets are closely tied to attribution theory – describing how successes and failures are attributed (e.g., Dweck & Yeager, 2021; Zhang et al., 2021) – it would be interesting to investigate whether individuals who have reached the final stage of the program exhibit more growth-oriented beliefs about their abilities compared to those who did not get that far. Unfortunately, as each season differs from the others quite significantly (e.g., different jury members), it seems problematic to aggregate observations from multiple editions. Moreover, the relatively lower reliability of the mixed mindsets assessment indicates that this type of belief was less precisely captured than the two other mindset forms, so these measures should be interpreted with caution. The study specifically focused on

countries with robust differences in collectivism and individualism (Oyserman et al., 2002). However, it would be valuable to expand this investigation with additional countries and a more comprehensive measurement of cultural dimensions. While the binary perspective of collectivism and individualism is widely used in cross-cultural studies (e.g., Ahn et al., 2016), the intensity of these dimensions fluctuates over time (Taras et al. 2012) and additional social dimensions could be considered (e.g., Tang et al., 2016). For example, it seems reasonable to assume that dimensions such as power distance and attitude towards uncertainty (Rinne et al., 2012) could also significantly influence beliefs about one's abilities. Notably, it has already been shown that equality acceptance, which is conceptually close to the power distance dimension, is positively linked to the growth creative mindset (Tang et al., 2016). Ultimately, to fully understand how vicarious experiences delivered by media across cultures relate to mindsets, future research should bridge the gap between the screens and the viewers, investigating how the program's content directly impacts the audience's beliefs regarding the nature of abilities and how it is translated into behavior.

Conclusion

Media content can be an important source of information shaping our conception about the nature of our abilities: Are they malleable, fixed, or both? In "... Got Talent!", an internationally successful talent show, convictions regarding possibilities to develop abilities differed by culture. The results were coherent with previous empirical studies: Fixed mindsets were most prevalent in Polish judges, whereas Chinese and Polish performers expressed growth mindsets more strongly than American performers. In sum, analyzing media content can help to better understand cultural differences in implicit theories about talent development, with media not only reflecting an expression but potentially also as a powerful driver of these convictions. In the long run, this kind of research can provide valuable insights into the basis of

cultural variations in creative accomplishments, such as varying levels of innovation or different agentic approaches to tackling challenges across countries.

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